

Digital Storytelling on African Urbanisms US-UK Workshop

McDonald Institute for Archaeological Research

University of Cambridge

September 12-14, 2022

Report prepared by Rosie Campbell and Carla Klehm

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Overview

The Digital Storytelling on African Urbanisms US-UK workshop was held in at the McDonald Institute for Archaeological Research at the University of Cambridge, Cambridge, UK from September 12-14, 2022. The workshop was organized as part of the NEH/AHRC grant of the same name, which seeks to develop education initiatives that incorporate digitized archaeological materials and relational databases for use by, and use in, the Global South. In particular, the project worked in close coordination with the *metsemegologolo* project, based at the University of Witwatersrand, University of Pretoria, and KwaZulu Natal Museum, all in South Africa, and the University of Cambridge.

The workshop brought together archaeological and geospatial experts from six different institutions to discuss how *metsemegologolo* might serve as a model for similar efforts, reviewing its successes and challenges to date and providing recommendations for future efforts. The morning of the first day focused on an overview of the *metsemegologolo* project. Representatives from *metsemegologolo* outlined the near-term and long-term objectives from the project and the variety of educational themes the project was hoping to emphasize. Since over a year had passed since the NEH/AHRC collaboration was initially proposed, *metsemegologolo* updated the group on progress, such as digital curations and planned activities, as well as provided an internal assessment of current needs. These needs provided a base for engagement with the US workshop contributors, from the Center for Advanced Spatial Technologies (CAST) at the University of Arkansas, for potential avenues for collaboration. The first afternoon reviewed technological and cultural barriers that digital initiatives such as *metsemegologolo* face in South Africa, and in the Global South more widely. The group examined comparative digital projects that involved spatial archives and/or digital storytelling components that focused on archaeology and African history and the history of various marginalized communities in the United States. CAST representatives presented their experiences with building a relational database for a WWII Japanese-American internment camp, Rohwer, which was also the focus of the comparative projects review (<https://risingabove.cast.uark.edu>). The second day involved a review of the archival structure of the *metsemegologolo* database. Discussion was oriented around the process of digital archiving of archaeological and ethnographic objects, associated datasets, maps, written documents, and audio and visual recordings. The group discussed the

types of spatial and nonspatial data the project involved and the digitization and visualization methods the project was using; reviewed the project standards for data collection, paradata, and metadata and the workflow pipelines; and, at a macro level, begin to think about the intended userbase, future scaling and efficiency efforts, and potential issues with storage, access, and sustainability. The final day focused on how metsemegologolo might be mobilized for digital storytelling. The group discussed best practices for storytelling, especially for doing so successfully in the Global South. Key to this debate was considering the use of ESRI StoryMaps versus an open-source platform such as Omeka; reflecting on colonial legacies in Africa and how best to encourage multiple narratives and interpretations; and integrating topical themes into the national (RSA) history curriculum. The afternoon was spent consolidating the summaries from the workshop, identifying next phases of collaborations, and preparing for a planned webinar on digital storytelling in March 2023.

Workshop attendees included:

- Mahmoud Abdelrazek (University College of London)
- Ella Baudin (University of Cambridge)
- Rosie Campbell (University of Cambridge)
- Anton Coetzee (University of Witwatersrand)
- Carla Klehm (University of Arkansas)
- Stefania Merlo (University of Cambridge)
- Malcolm Williamson (University of Arkansas)
- Katie Wyatt (University of Arkansas)

Online participants included:

- Chris Buirski (University of Pretoria)
- Amanda Esterhuysen (University of Witwatersrand)
- Chiara Singh (Kwa Zulu Natal Museum)
- Yanda Nhlapo (University of Pretoria)
- Justine Wintjes (Kwa Zulu Natal Museum)

Final workshop recommendations for the metsemegologolo project included:

- Develop documentation to describe how the site was built, the workflows used for adding data, etc. Make those standards/requirements explicit and consider avenues for further automation on data cleaning and checking, if data will be uploaded in bulk
- Addition of elements to archive to enhance visualisation of data spatially (e.g., timelines)
- Consider the separation of the archive and curation platform due to diversity of resource levels, technologies, etc.
- Consider scalability of archival products into different curatorial platforms
- Moving forward, provide greater clarification/specification of classes of objects and archived items
- Elaborate object descriptions, soften language to increase understanding and incorporate multilingual database for item searching
- Orient archive navigation and curation use for secondary school student users at a variety of competency levels (basic/advanced, interactive/static)

- Create short prompts for student storytelling in museum setting or independently with the archive, as jumping off points for students to make their own curations and/or explore further
- Develop small, sample curations and strategies for student engagement and competition
- Identify median target ability and ideas for engaging higher and lower level of ability: emphasize different skill sets within the activity, accommodate differing prior education style, collaboration considerations in the museum setting
- Further review of user interaction with pages, following the review in MSc thesis by Brenda Maina (University of Pretoria), and consider the actual length of time to make a Storymap (assessment of usability) to inform future testing of curatorial prompts
- Consider centralizing storytelling efforts within museums to utilize existing and potential infrastructure and collections
- Plan towards publicizing the existence and importance of the archive and storytelling capabilities
- Address lingering storage issues that consider cost and long-term sustainability, as it is currently hosted in Germany (but with potential South African partners moving forward)
- Clarify definitions of “low resource environments” and related (often conflated) concepts, particularly regarding gradient of various resources, particularly in a quadrant conceptualization (resource, technical education), for publication within the digital humanities community

An unabridged version of the workshop notes is available upon request, to cklehm@uark.edu.
